

THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC DEBT ON ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract. *This study analyzes the relationship between public debt and economic sustainability in Uzbekistan over the period 2014–2023 using a multiple regression model and an Economic Stability Index (ESI). The results indicate that public debt has a moderate negative effect on economic stability, while fiscal balance and inflation exert stronger destabilizing impacts. The findings suggest that wise debt management combined with fiscal discipline is essential for long-term economic sustainability.*

Key words: *Public debt, economic sustainability, fiscal balance, trade balance, macroeconomic stability.*

Introduction. Globalization and recurrent global financial crises have contributed to a significant expansion of public debt in both developing countries and advanced economies.

Government borrowing is commonly used to finance infrastructure development, implement emergency measures during economic crises, and improve social welfare. Public debt is the total outstanding liabilities of the general government at a given point in time.[1] While public debt can serve as an important fiscal instrument, excessive accumulation raises serious concerns regarding macroeconomic stability and long-term economic sustainability. Public debt is divided into two types: domestic debts and external debt.[2] Domestic debt consists of loans received by the state from the issuance of bonds and other securities within the country, and from various extra-budgetary funds (insurance fund, unemployment insurance fund, pension fund), while external debt is debt received from foreign countries, individuals and legal entities in them, as well as from international financial organizations.

Economic sustainability refers to an economy's capacity to maintain stable economic growth, fiscal balance, and social welfare over the long term without creating excessive financial imbalances or imposing undue burdens on future generations.[3] From this perspective, public debt represents a double-edged fiscal instrument. When managed prudently and directed toward productive investments, public debt may enhance economic sustainability. However, when debt exceeds sustainable thresholds, it can undermine fiscal stability, crowd out private investment, increase interest payment obligations, and heighten vulnerability to external economic shocks.

Moreover, high levels of public debt may weaken investor confidence and result in higher interest rates.

Debt statistics play a crucial role in assessing the sustainability of a government's fiscal policy. They provide essential information for determining whether fiscal adjustments are necessary to avoid potential debt distress or default. Furthermore, public debt data facilitate international comparisons, allowing countries to benchmark their fiscal positions and identify emerging risks.

Accurate and transparent debt statistics are therefore vital for effective monetary and fiscal policymaking, particularly with regard to taxation and government expenditure decisions.

Overall, public debt indicators constitute a key component of macroeconomic analysis and are indispensable for informed decision-making by policymakers, investors, and the public.

According to World Bank methodology being used since 2011, the following factors are taken into account when assessing the sustainability of public debt: budget risk; composition of public debt (domestic and external, term structure, dependence on currency risks); level of economic development and fiscal capacity of the state; external financial conditions, global risks and other relevant indicators.

Literature review

The existing literature has examined various aspects of the relationship between public debt and economic stability, offering differing theoretical perspectives. The neoclassical view generally adopts a pessimistic stance, emphasizing the negative effects of high public debt on economic performance. Prominent studies by Reinhart and Rogoff analyze historical episodes of financial crises and highlight the adverse consequences of excessive debt accumulation before and after crises. Additionally, Reinhart and Rogoff explore the possibility of a persistent relationship between high gross central government debt levels, economic growth and inflation. The authors report the existence of a weak link between growth and low levels of debt, but when debt ratio is over 90%, the economies' growth rates are on average one percent lower than otherwise. [4] In contrast, the Keynesian perspective suggests that public debt may have a positive impact on economic sustainability, particularly when the interest rate (r) is lower than the economic growth rate (g), as emphasized by Blanchard [5] Under such conditions, debt-financed public investment can support growth without jeopardizing fiscal sustainability.

When exploring the influence of high public debt on long-run growth, based on a panel data of advanced and developing countries over 38 years, Kumar and Jaejoon (2010) [6] reach two important conclusions: an inverse relationship between the initial level of government debt and economic growth rate.

Methodology

- Analytical method – analyzing relationships among public debt, fiscal balance, inflation, trade balance and economic growth.

- Secondary data collection: given data in this paper is usually based on statistical databases and annual reports of World Bank, OECD, IMF.

- Comparative analysis: comparison of public debt of Uzbekistan during nine-year period and correlation between economic stability index and public debt and other factors.

Table 1. Calculation of Economic stability index of Uzbekistan based on proposed regression.

Year	Debt/GDP	Inflation	Trade balance/GDP	Fiscal balance/GDP	ESI
2014	6.09	9.3	-3	1.9	0.479876
2015	6.72	8.8	-2.36	-0.3	0.567339
2016	8.19	8.1	-2.75	0.7	0.538149
2017	17.26	13.9	-2.81	1	0.290284
2018	17.46	17.5	-10.89	1.6	0.316584
2019	25.38	14.5	-10.31	-0.3	0.393062

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2020	33.67	12.9	-10.28	-2.9	0.468251
2021	31.73	10.9	-12.5	-4.1	0.629926
2022	30.53	11.5	-14.37	-3.7	0.642631
2023	32.18	10	-15.93	-4	0.708808

Based on Countryeconomy.com, worldscorecard.com, fred.stlouisfed.org data calculated by author.

This study constructed an Economic Stability Index (ESI) using normalized macroeconomic indicators and applied a multiple regression model to evaluate the impact of key macroeconomic factors on economic stability over the period 2014–2023.

The regression results confirm that economic stability is a multidimensional phenomenon, influenced simultaneously by fiscal, monetary, and external sector indicators. All explanatory variables exhibit negative coefficients, indicating that an increase in macroeconomic imbalances leads to a deterioration of economic stability.

Interpretation of regression coefficients. The estimated regression equation is:

$$ESI = 0.806 - 0.009(\text{Public debt/GDP}) - 0.027(\text{Inflation}) - 0.018(\text{Trade Balance /GDP})$$

The coefficient of -0.009 indicates that, *ceteris paribus*, a 1 percentage point increase in the public debt-to-GDP ratio reduces the Economic Stability Index by 0.009 units. Although the magnitude of this effect is smaller compared to other variables, it suggests that rising public debt gradually undermines macroeconomic stability by increasing fiscal vulnerability and limiting policy flexibility.

Inflation has a coefficient of -0.027 , implying that a 1 percentage point increase in inflation reduces the ESI by 0.027 units, holding other factors constant.

This result highlights inflation as one of the most influential destabilizing factors, reflecting its adverse effects on purchasing power, investment decisions, and overall macroeconomic predictability.

The trade balance coefficient (-0.018) shows that a worsening trade balance (larger deficit) significantly decreases economic stability.

Persistent trade deficits weaken external sustainability by increasing reliance on foreign financing and exposing the economy to external shocks, thereby negatively affecting the ESI.

The largest coefficient in absolute value (-0.042) belongs to the fiscal balance variable.

This implies that fiscal imbalances have the strongest destabilizing effect among the considered factors. A deterioration of the fiscal balance directly affects government credibility, debt dynamics, and macroeconomic confidence, making fiscal discipline a key pillar of economic stability.

Based on coefficient magnitudes, the relative influence of variables on economic stability can be ranked as follows:

1. Fiscal balance (strongest impact)
2. Inflation
3. Trade balance

This ranking indicates that short-term macroeconomic management (fiscal and monetary stability) plays a more decisive role in determining economic stability than debt accumulation alone.

Table 2. Economic stability index of Uzbekistan (2014-2023)

**Based on Countryeconomy.com, worldscorecard.com, fred.stlouisfed.org data calculated by author*

Conclusion.

This study analyzed the influence of public debt on economic sustainability in Uzbekistan from 2014 to 2023 by developing an Economic Stability Index (ESI) and used a multiple regression model. The results of the regression show that public debt has a moderately detrimental impact on economic stability. Fiscal balance has the most detrimental impact on economic stability among the explanatory factors. The significant negative coefficient linked to the decline in the fiscal balance emphasizes how important fiscal restraint is to preserving macroeconomic credibility and long-term debt dynamics. Because of its detrimental effects on purchasing power, investment choices, and macroeconomic predictability, inflation also stands out as a major destabilizing factor.

Furthermore, by making the economy more reliant on outside funding and making it more vulnerable to shocks from around the world, persistent trade deficits have a detrimental effect on economic stability.

Overall, the findings suggest that, with careful management, good fiscal policies, efficient inflation control, and external sector balance, public debt can coexist with economic sustainability.

To ensure that public debt acts as a supporting tool rather than a barrier to long-term economic viability, Uzbekistan must promote fiscal discipline, increase the effectiveness of public spending, and retain macroeconomic stability.

The list of literature

1. IMF, Government Finance Statistics Manual (GFSM 2014)
2. Darslik / B.I. Nurmuxamedova, Sh.K. Xamdorov; – T.: “Iqtisod-Moliya”, 2020. – 428 b.
3. OECD Economic Outlook, OECD Framework for Policy Action on Inclusive Growth, OECD Well-Being Framework
4. Reinhart, C., & Rogoff, K. (2009). This Time Is Different: Eight Centuries of Financial Folly. Princeton University Press
5. Blanchard, O., & Johnson, D. R. (2013). Macroeconomics (6th ed.). Pearson.
6. Kumar, M. S., & Woo, J. (2010). Public Debt and Growth (IMF Working Paper No. 10/174)

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7. CountryEconomy. Economic and financial data by country from <https://countryeconomy.com>
8. Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis. FRED: Federal Reserve Economic Data from <https://fred.stlouisfed.org>
9. WorldScorecard. Global economic and development indicators, from <https://worldscorecard.com>

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